

The impact of triclosan on renal and pulmonary systems: A comprehensive review

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Abstract

Triclosan (TCS) is a widely used antimicrobial agent found in personal care products, household items, and industrial applications. While its effectiveness as a bacteriostat is well documented, emerging research highlights its potential toxicity as it is an endocrine-disrupting chemical (EDC) that affects hormonal balance and is absorbed through skin contact, ingestion, and inhalation. This review underscores the potential health hazards of long-term TCS exposure, particularly in disrupting kidney and lung function. Experimental research in rodents and aquatic species has demonstrated that TCS exposure leads to weight loss, renal fibrosis, structural alterations, oxidative stress, and apoptosis. Histological and biochemical analyses reveal increased blood urea nitrogen and creatinine levels, indicating impaired kidney function. Pulmonary toxicity studies link TCS exposure to asthma, allergic reactions, and lung inflammation. Given its extensive use beyond regulated applications, future research should focus on understanding its long-term effects and developing safer formulations to mitigate public health risks.

Keywords: Triclosan Toxicity; Renal Dysfunction; Pulmonary Toxicity; Endocrine Disruptor; Oxidative Stress; Environmental Health

1. Introduction

Triclosan is a nonionic compound that appears as an off-white, odourless, and tasteless powder. Its chemical name is 2,4,4'-trichloro-2'-hydroxydiphenyl ether, and its molecular formula is $C_{12}H_7Cl_3O_2$ [1]. The substance has a long history as a potent bacteriostat and antiseptic. Its effectiveness and safety have made it a widely used component in personal care products designed for skin application, including soaps, deodorants, and skin cleansers [2].

Triclosan (TCS) was initially introduced into the healthcare industry in 1972 and later became toothpaste formulations in Europe by 1985 [1]. Products like soaps, cosmetics, and shampoos are regulated by the FDA, but this oversight only extends to antiseptic washes intended for non-medical use, such as antibacterial hand soaps for household settings. As a result, TCS continues to be used extensively in numerous commercial products that fall outside FDA regulation, particularly in items like furniture, clothing, and kitchenware, including knives and cutting boards [3].

TCS exerts its effect on the phospholipid membrane by acting like a detergent, disrupting the stability of lipid structures [4]. However, some bacterial species have evolved intricate mechanisms to counter the toxic effects of TCS. A key strategy involves non-specific multidrug resistance (MDR) efflux pumps [5].

1.1. General study of triclosan

Triclosan is classified as an endocrine disruptor (EDC) due to its potential to affect the estrogen, androgen, and thyroid systems, leading to hormonal imbalances [6,7,8]. Humans can come in contact with triclosan via contact on skin or

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even through oral consumption [9,10]. TCS in the environment is predominantly encountered through contaminated water, food, or animal sources [11].

Multiple studies have indicated that TCS exposure may promote liver tumor development in mice by increasing liver cell proliferation, inducing fibrogenesis, and elevating oxidative stress [12,13].

TCS exhibits toxic effects, such as reduced cell viability accompanied by morphological alterations in L2 rat epithelial lung cells. Additionally, a single intratracheal instillation at a dose of 1 mg/kg induced acute inflammation and increased lung permeability [14].

The kidney plays a crucial role in detoxification; however, studies indicate that exposure to environmental pollutants can contribute to early kidney damage, increase the risk of chronic kidney disease (CKD), and potentially progress to end-stage renal disease (ESRD) [15,16]. Moreover, higher levels of TCS exposure may increase the likelihood of developing asthma, allergies, and food sensitization [17]. It has also been suggested that frequent use of antimicrobial products is associated with an increased risk of wheezing and allergic rhinitis [18].

2. Source

This review presents a thorough assessment of triclosan's toxicity and associated risks, with a particular emphasis on its effects on the kidneys and lungs. The literature includes both experimental and non-experimental using databases such as PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Science Direct, EMBASE and Google Scholar, covering studies published between 2010 and 2024.

2.1. TCS on renal function

Figure 1 TCS mode of entry and its renal toxicity [19]

2.2. Survey Based Studies

The potential for early kidney damage due to environmental endocrine-disrupting chemicals (EDCs) and heavy metals was explored in a study using data from the Second Korean National Environmental Health Survey (2012–2014), they reported a positive association between higher levels of TCS and elevated urinary β 2-microglobulin (β 2M), a marker of kidney injury [16]. Similarly, the correlation between personal care product usage and urinary TCS concentrations was studied in 5962 participants aged 3 to 80 years, based on data from the Korean National Environmental Health Survey. The study found that men use fewer personal care products than women, resulting in higher TCS concentrations in females. Among urinary chemicals, the concentrations decreased in the order of propyl paraben > TCS > methyl paraben [20].

2.3. Body weights and Anatomical changes

A study examined the dermal toxicity of TCS where the mice received 0, 5.8, 12.5, 27, 58, and 125 mg/kg/bw for 13 weeks where substantial reductions in average body weights was seen. Additionally, Dermal fibrosis, inflammation, epidermal hyperplasia, necrosis, ulceration, and parakeratosis were observed. Low kidney weight in males and high in females indicated kidney damage [21]. Channa punctatus fish was exposed to TCS concentrations of 0.37 mg/L and 1.11 mg/L for 96 hours and depletion in the kidney was 36.31% in sub-lethal and 55.21% in lethal depletion of carbohydrate levels. This suggested that TCS exposure enhances glycogenolysis and glycolytic activity to meet increased energy demands under stress conditions. [22]. 30 male Sprague-Dawley and 15 bighead carp rats were exposed to TCS doses

of 0.25, 25, 250, or 750 mg/kg for 60 days and 15 days, respectively. The results reported a reduction in body weight, kidney weight necrosis of tubules, and increased urinary spaces. [15, 23]. The studies collectively demonstrate that exposure to TCS can result in notable physiological and anatomical alterations, such as reductions in body weight, organ-specific damage, and disruptions in metabolic processes across different species

2.4. Histological and Biochemical Alterations

According to [24] TCS exposure can lead to structural and functional alterations in the renal cortex, 200 mg/kg dose of TCS for 6 weeks was given to 30 adult male albino rats which resulted in significant histological abnormalities, including increased cellularity in the glomeruli and disorganization of the tubules. Moreover, blood urea nitrogen and serum creatinine levels were elevated, indicating impaired renal function.

Elevated levels of blood urea nitrogen and creatinine, alterations in Bowman's space, tubular occlusion, and epithelial cell degeneration were seen in rats and in mice renal hypertrophy showed a higher prevalence of apoptotic cells after 8 months of exposure to 0.008% TCS [15, 12]. Similarly, another study investigated the toxic effects of four samples of reclaimed water i.e. control, WTE, WTI, and MBRP (Membrane bioreactor permeate) on human embryonic kidney cells for 24 hours. The reclaimed water samples disrupted the levels of proteins involved in cell division and death, suggesting their harmful impact on kidney cells [25].

These studies collectively point to significant health risks from TCS exposure, with observed kidney damage, which includes fibrosis, cellular apoptosis, and impaired organ function, demonstrating the widespread toxic impact of triclosan.

2.5. Oxidative stress and Cell apoptosis

An in vitro study investigated TCS effects on human renal glomerular endothelial cells where cells were exposed to 5 - 100 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ for 24 hours. TCS induced oxidative stress in endothelial cells, potentially leading to cell death by disrupting the PI3K/Akt signaling pathway. Apoptosis rates were 81.6%, 67.7%, and 40.5% at TCS concentrations of 15, 20, and 30 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, respectively, indicating that TCS significantly triggers cell death in a dose-dependent manner [26]. In the same way, increased high mobility group box 1 (HMGB1) protein expression confirmed tubular necrosis in rats [15].

TCS was orally given to 30 male C57BL/6 mice at doses of 10 and 100 mg/kg/day for 10- 13 weeks which led to renal injury, increased oxidative stress markers like malondialdehyde (MDA) levels, along with reduced expression of superoxide dismutase (SOD) and total cholesterol (TCHO) pro-inflammatory cytokines, and fibrotic markers in a dose-dependent manner. Additionally, lipid accumulation and disrupted fatty acid metabolism and alterations in gut microbiota in mouse kidneys were seen which further can contribute to renal dysfunction [19,27] Taken together, these studies demonstrate that TCS exposure induces oxidative stress

apoptosis, and renal injury in a dose-dependent manner, with significant impacts on inflammation, fibrosis, and metabolic disruptions, further highlighting its potential to cause renal dysfunction

2.6. TCS on pulmonary function

Figure 2 TCS mode of entry and pulmonary toxicity [28]

2.7. Survey-based and Case Studies

Panel studies highlighted a strong connection between TCS exposure and allergic disease occurrence in preschool-aged children [17,29]. Relationship between prenatal exposure to environmental phenol and phthalate biomarkers and respiratory or allergic conditions in children was examined studies found that prenatal exposure to TCS was linked to a higher likelihood of an asthma diagnosis due to activation of Bmp4 inducing lung apoptosis and cyst like formation in lungs [30,31]. Urinary TCS levels were significantly associated with an increased prevalence of asthma exacerbations, as analyzed using data from 600 samples in the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) conducted between 2005 and 2010 [31]. A case study focused on a 26-year-old female with occupational asthma, who developed immediate asthmatic reactions triggered by exposure to Antibac cleaner containing triclosan. Serial peak flow

readings and specific inhalational challenges confirmed that TCS exposure contributed to allergic sensitivities to cleaning products and personal care items [32,33].

2.8. Anatomical and Histological Changes

Aerosol inhalation of TCS in rats over 28 days caused salivation, weight loss, nasal ulcers, severe inflammation, and histopathological changes in the nasal septum and larynx, with males and females equally affected at high concentrations [34]. In aquatic environments, TCS has also been shown to negatively impact respiratory systems. In one study, exposure of freshwater fish to sublethal concentrations of TCS caused significant gill damage, including thickened lamellae, swelling, and fusion, which impaired gas exchange [35].

Some studies found similar results in different species of fish where the authors observed an increase in lipid peroxidation (LPO) levels in the gills, suggesting oxidative stress. Higher concentrations caused 100% mortality and behavioural changes such as air gulping, mucous deposition, and hemorrhagic eyes, along with histopathological damage to the gills, including hyperplasia and lamellar disorganization, hypertrophy, lamellar fusion, ruptures, twisted, uplifted secondary lamellae, disorganization, and necrosis of epithelial cells [23,36,37,38].

2.9. Oxidative stress and Cell Death

In a study, dermal exposure to TCS in BALB/c mice co-sensitized with ovalbumin (OVA) led to heightened allergic responses and airway hyperreactivity [39]. Some studies evaluated the harmful effects of TCS in mitochondrial cells and lung epithelial cell where it caused mitochondrial depolarization, necrotic cell death and oxidative stress through interference with ATP synthesis, respiratory control and induced reactive oxygen species (ROS) production, further highlighting its capacity to induce pulmonary toxicity [40,41,42]. In an experiment with Spargue Dawley rats, single intratracheal instillation of TCS caused inflammation, acute lung injury, and elevated pulmonary toxicity markers, indicating its potential impact on lung function [14]. Similarly, TCS was found to promote epithelial-to-mesenchymal (ETM) transition in lung cancer cells, and mitochondrial depolarization by reducing E-cadherin levels and activating adhesion kinase, interfering with ATP synthesis, thereby enhancing the migration and growth of anoikis-resistant cancer cells [42, 43]. Another study demonstrated that the topical application of TCS (1–3%) on BALB/cAnTac mice and human skin tissue led to an enhanced immune

response, with upregulation of TSLP, IL-1 β , and TNF- α , and an increase in draining lymph node cellularity, indicating the potential for acute allergic reactions in the lungs [44].

The combined effects of TCS (185 mg/kg) and sodium fluoride (50 mg/kg) were investigated in rats, revealing oxidative stress, reduced antioxidant enzyme levels (SOD, CAT, and GSH), and upregulation of apoptotic genes in lung tissue. Interestingly, co-exposure to TCS and NaF resulted in less oxidative stress compared to individual exposures, suggesting a potential interaction that mitigates certain adverse effects [45].

The available literature suggests that TCS causes serious environmental problems, affecting the aquatic ecosystem and also severe health hazards to humans.

3. Conclusion

Exposure to triclosan, often found in personal care and household items, can have significant health implications. Elevated levels of TCS can damage the vital organs of the human body, including the liver, kidneys, and thyroid, hence damaging the organs and also causing hormonal imbalances. In the kidneys, it may result in the induction of oxidative stress and inflammation and interfere with the process of filtration as well as fluid regulation. Long-term exposure of TCS inhalation will also irritate the lung tissue, leading to risks for respiratory problems like inflammation and

breathing difficulty, particularly among asthma or other respiratory-sensitive people. While these findings highlight serious concerns, further research is crucial to fully understand triclosan's long-term effects on human health and its impact on different populations.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Jones RD, Jampani HB, Newman JL, Lee AS. Triclosan: A review of effectiveness and safety in health care settings. *Am J Infect Control*. 2000;28(2):184–96.
- [2] Dayan AD. Risk assessment of triclosan [Irgasan] in human breast milk. *Food Chem Toxicol*. 2007;45(1):125–9.
- [3] Papavasiliopoulos RK, Kang S. Bibliometric analysis: The effects of triclosan on human health. *Toxics*. 2022;10(9):523.
- [4] Alfili MA, Lee MH. Triclosan: An update on biochemical and molecular mechanisms. *Oxid Med Cell Longev*. 2019;1–28.
- [5] Shrestha P, Zhang Y, Chen WJ, Wong TY. Triclosan: Antimicrobial mechanisms, antibiotics interactions, clinical applications, and human health. *J Environ Sci Health*. 2020;38:245–68.
- [6] Paul KB, Hedge JM, Bansal R, Zoeller RT, Peter R, DeVito MJ, Crofton KM. Developmental triclosan exposure decreases maternal, fetal, and early neonatal thyroxine: a dynamic and kinetic evaluation of a putative mode-of-action. *Toxicology*. 2012;300:31–45.
- [7] Louis GW, Hallinger DR, Stoker TE. The effect of triclosan on the uterotrophic response to extended doses of ethinyl estradiol in the weanling rat. *Reprod Toxicol*. 2013;36:71–7.
- [8] Tarnow P, Tralau T, Hunecke D, Luch A. Effects of triclocarban on the transcription of estrogen, androgen, and aryl hydrocarbon receptor responsive genes in human breast cancer cells. *Toxicol In Vitro*. 2013;27(5):1467–75.
- [9] Yueh MF, Tukey RH. Triclosan: A widespread environmental toxicant with many biological effects. *Annu Rev Pharmacol Toxicol*. 2016;56(1):251–72.
- [10] Chen J, Meng XZ, Bergman A, Halden RU. Nationwide reconnaissance of five parabens, triclosan, triclocarban and its transformation products in sewage sludge from China. *J Hazard Mater*. 2019;365:502–10.
- [11] Milanović M, Đurić L, Milošević N, Milić N. Comprehensive insight into triclosan—from widespread occurrence to health outcomes. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int*. 2023;30(10):25119–40.
- [12] Yueh MF, Taniguchi K, Chen S, Evans RM, Hammock BD, Karin M, Tukey RH. The commonly used antimicrobial additive triclosan is a liver tumor promoter. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2014;111(48):17200–5.
- [13] Wang Z, Li X, Klaunig JE. Investigation of the mechanism of triclosan-induced mouse liver tumors. *Regul Toxicol Pharmacol*. 2017;86:137–47.
- [14] Kwon JT, Yang YS, Kang MS, Seo GB, Lee DH, Yang MJ, Shim I, Kim HM, Kim P, Choi K, Lee K. Pulmonary toxicity screening of triclosan in rats after intratracheal instillation. *J Toxicol Sci*. 2013;38(3):471–5.
- [15] Ena L, Lim JS, Son JY, Park YJ, Lee YH, Kim JY, Kwack SJ, Lee BM, Ahn MY, Kim HS. Evaluation of subchronic exposure to triclosan on hepatorenal and reproductive toxicities in prepubertal male rats. *J Toxicol Environ Health*. 2018;81:421–31.
- [16] Zheng LY, Sanders AP, Saland JM, Wright RO, Arora M. Exposure to environmental pollutants and a marker of early kidney injury in the general population: results of a nationally representative cross-sectional study based on the Korean National Environmental Health Survey (KoNEHS) 2012–2014. *Environ Res*. 2017;1(681):175–82.
- [17] Spanier AJ, Fausnight T, Camacho TF, Braun JM. The associations of triclosan and paraben exposure with allergen sensitization and wheeze in children. *Allergy Asthma Proc*. 2014;35(6):475–81.
- [18] Hong S, Kwon HJ, Choi WJ, Lim WR, Kim J, Kim K. Association between exposure to antimicrobial household products and allergic symptoms. *Environ Health Toxicol*. 2014;29:e2014017.

- [19] Huang W, Cao G, Deng C, Chen Y, Wang T, Chen D, Cai Z. Adverse effects of triclosan on kidney in mice: implication of lipid metabolism disorders. *J Environ Sci*. 2023;124:481–90.
- [20] Lim S. The associations between personal care products use and urinary concentrations of phthalates, parabens, and triclosan in various age groups: The Korean National Environmental Health Survey Cycle 3 (2015–2017). *Sci Total Environ*. 2020;742:140640.
- [21] Fang JL, Vanlandingham MM, Juliar BE, Olson GR, Patton RE, Beland FA. Dose-response assessment of the dermal toxicity of triclosan in B6C3F1 mice. *Toxicol Res*. 2015;4(4):867–77.
- [22] Kola RK, Yalavarthy PD. A study of total carbohydrate modifications induced by triclosan on *Channa punctatus* (Bloch). *Am J Sci Med Res*. 2017;3(4):15–8.
- [23] Akram R, Ghaffar A, Hussain R, Khan I, Santana VLDA, Mehmood K, Naz S, Iqbal R, Imran HM, Qamar MR, Zhu H. Haematological, serum biochemistry, histopathological and mutagenic impacts of triclosan on fish (bighead carp). *Agrobiological Records*. 2022;7:18–28.
- [24] Hassan ZA, Abd El-Haleem MR, Mansour GN. Effect of triclosan on the renal cortex of adult male albino rats and the possible protective role of ellagic acid: Histological and biochemical study. *J Environ Sci Health B*. 2014;58(4):345–56.
- [25] Ren X, Kou YY, Kim T, Chae KJ, Ng HY. Toxicity study of reclaimed water on human embryonic kidney cells. *Chemosphere*. 2017; 08:390-8.
- [26] Ma Y, Chen C, Wang JB, Cheng JL, Shen S, Chen X, Huo JS. Triclosan-induced oxidative stress injury and apoptosis by regulating the PI3K/Akt/Caspase-3 signaling pathway in human renal glomerular endothelial cells. *Biomed Environ Sci*. 2022;35(6):547-51.
- [27] Zhuang J, Chen Q, Xu L, Chen X. Effects of chronic triclosan exposure on nephrotoxicity and gut microbiota dysbiosis in adult mice. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf*. 2024;271:115866.
- [28] Li Q, Xu S, Qiao Y, Wang F, Zhao J, Wu L, Ge H. Prenatal triclosan exposure impairs mammalian lung branching morphogenesis through activating Bmp4 signalling. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf*. 2023;256:114896.
- [29] Lin MH, Chiu SY, Ho WC, Chi KH, Liu TY, et al. Effect of triclosan on the pathogenesis of allergic diseases among children. *J Expo Sci Environ Epidemiol*. 2022;32:60–68.
- [30] Buckley JP, Quirós-Alcalá L, Teitelbaum SL, Calafat AM, Wolff MS, Engel SM. Associations of prenatal environmental phenol and phthalate biomarkers with respiratory and allergic diseases among children aged 6 and 7 years. *Environ Int*. 2018;115:79–88.
- [31] Savage JH, Johns CB, Hauser R, Litonjua AA. Urinary triclosan levels and recent asthma exacerbations. *Ann Allergy Asthma Immunol*. 2014;112(2):179–181.
- [32] Walters GI, Robertson AS, Moore VC, Burge PS. Occupational asthma caused by sensitization to a cleaning product containing triclosan. *Ann Allergy Asthma Immunol*. 2017;118(3):370–371.
- [33] Darbre PD. Respiratory irritation and sensitization. *Pers Care Prod Hum Health*. 2023;9:211–30.
- [34] Yang YS, Kwon JT, Shim I, Kim HM, Kim P, Kim JC, Lee K. Evaluation of toxicity to triclosan in rats following 28 days of exposure to aerosol inhalation. *Regul Toxicol Pharmacol*. 2015;71:259-68.
- [35] Ann MJ, Kaippallil JD. Histopathological changes in the gill of freshwater teleost, *Channa striatus* (Bloch) on exposure to endocrine disruptor chemical, triclosan. *J Exp Zool India*. 2018;21(2):901–5.
- [36] Priyatha CV, Chitra KC. Acute toxicity of triclosan on the native freshwater fish, *Anabas testudineus* (Bloch, 1792): behavioral alterations and histopathological lesions. *Int J Life Sci*. 2018;6(1):166-72.
- [37] Hemalatha D, Nataraj B, Rangasamy B, Shobana C, Ramesh M. DNA damage and physiological responses in an Indian major carp exposed to an antimicrobial agent triclosan. *Fish Physiol Biochem*. 2019;45(4):1463–84.
- [38] Paul T, Shukla S, Kumar K, Poojary N, Samiyappan M, Kumar S. Effects of temperature and pH on acute toxicity of triclosan in *Pangasianodon hypophthalmus*. *Am J Sci Med Res*. 2019;90(3):677-85.
- [39] Anderson SE, Franko J, Kashon ML, Anderson KL, Hubbs AF, Lukomska E, Meade BJ. Exposure to triclosan augments the allergic response to ovalbumin in a mouse model of asthma. *Toxicol Sci*. 2012;132(1):96–106.
- [40] Kuan JT, Lee M, Seo GB, Kim HM, Shim I, Lee DH, Kim T, Seo JK, Kim P, Choi K. Cytotoxic effects of air freshener biocides in lung epithelial cells. *Nat Prod Commun*. 2013;8(9):1301–4.

- [41] Kwon JT, Seo GB, Kim HM, Shim I, Lee B, Jung JY, Kim P, Choi K. Evaluation of comparative cytotoxicity of spray-type chemicals used in household products. *Mol Cell Toxicol.* 2013;9:51–6.
- [42] Ajaoa C, Andersson MA, Teplova VV, Nagy S, Gahmberg CG, Andersson LC, Hautaniemi M, Kakasi B, Roivainen M, Salkinoja-Salonen M. Mitochondrial toxicity of triclosan on mammalian cells. *Toxicology Reports.* 2015;2:624–37.
- [43] Winitthana T, Lawanprasert S, Chanvorachote P. Triclosan potentiates epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition in anoikis-resistant human lung cancer cells. *PLoS ONE.* 2014;9(10):e11085.
- [44] Marshall NB, Lukomska E, Long CM, Kashon ML, Sharpnack DD, Nayak AP, Anderson KL, Meade BJ, Anderson SE. Triclosan induces thymic stromal lymphopoietin in the skin promoting Th2 allergic responses. *Toxicol Sci.* 2015;147(1):127–39.
- [45] Mohammed AT, Mohamed AA, Ali H. Pulmonary apoptotic and oxidative damaging effects of triclosan alone or in combination with fluoride in Sprague Dawley rats. *Acta Histochemica.* 2017;119(4):357-363.